

THE CONTRIBUTION OF ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS TO THE IMPROVEMENT OF EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to investigate the influence of the education, training, motivation, facilities, discipline, and working environment on the performance of employees and to know the dominant variables that affect the performance of the employee. The analysis of the data used by researchers was a multiple linear regression analysis, F test, t-test, and the coefficient of determination. The sample used in this study was the census sample, the sample used was 42 people. The results of the analysis stated that education, training, motivation, facilities, discipline, and working environment had an impact on the performance of employees and working environment was the most dominant factor that influence performance of employees.

Keywords: Working environment, Employee performance

1. INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, the challenge faced is globalization with all of its implications. Resources owned by companies such as capital, methods, and machinery would not be able to provide good results if not supported by human resources that have good performance as well. In order for a company to succeed, compete, and survive the company must obtain capable and competent human resources.

With this competition, it is expected that the company not only provide advanced technology but also reliable human resources. The biggest real threat for human resources today is the enormous challenges as well as the changes taking place around it. (Arisanti, 2013)

Employee performance might be influenced by several factors such as salary, allowances, facilities, incentives, bonuses, education, training, experience, age, and discipline. If these factors are considered well by the company then the level of employee performance obtained by the company will be maximized. (Arisanti, 2013).

The effect of education on employee performance is that employees are able to perform their duties and responsibilities in accordance with standard operating procedures (SOP) that have been established by the company. In addition, the company must also provide training for employees so they are capable of working effectively and efficiently, and the training must also in accordance with employee education background. The better the education and training programs undertaken by the managers of the organization the more skilled the employees are in doing their job. (K, Awaluddin, dkk. 2013)

The success of a company depends on the performance of its employees. Without a good performance, the results produced by the company either in the form of goods or services will make consumers dissatisfied with the companies' production and service. Therefore, the most important factor to improve employee performance is work motivation. (Murdiyanto, 2012)

Employee performance is also affected by the facilities provided by the company. Facility is a means to promote and facilitate the implementation of employee functions and duties. Each company should provide a fun facility that turns out this facility is able to improve employee performance. (Murdiyanto, 2012)

Discipline is very beneficial for the interests of the company and the employees. For the company, the existence of discipline will ensure the maintenance of rules and smooth implementation of duties and responsibilities of employees. For employees, there will be a pleasant working atmosphere that adds spirit at work and can improve employee performance. (Sutrisno, 2011)

Another factor that affects employee performance is the working environment; working environment can be viewed from the aspect of employee relationships with fellow colleagues and with superiors, and also comfortable and safe working environment for employees. A good working environment will have a positive impact that can improve employee spirit and performance. (Murdiyanto, 2012)

Graha Puger Sehat Clinic is a company in the field of health services that prioritize patients' comfort and safety. As a company engaged in health services, Graha Puger Sehat Clinic requires trained and competent human resources in accordance with the position and the needs of the Clinic.

Graha Puger Sehat Clinic is relatively new company, of course currently it still encounters various problems related to employment issues, mainly due to low employee performance that is influenced by the level of education, training, motivation, facilities, discipline, and working environment.

There are several factors affecting employee performance such as education, training, motivation, facilities, salary, incentive, bonuses, experience, age, allowances, and discipline. Employee performance is something achieved

by employees or workers so that the company's goals are achieved in accordance with the vision and mission of the company.

There were 11 previous studies that have been conducted i.e. first by Kurusi, Alam, Yusuf Mardiana in 2013 with the research variables were facility, level of education, and working discipline, and the conclusion obtained was that facility and education had positive and significant effect on employee performance. The second was by Arisanti in 2013 with the research variables were education, training, motivation, and facilities, and the conclusion obtained was that training had positive and significant effect on employee performance. The third was by Hardjono in 2013 with the research variables were motivation, working discipline, and working ability, and the conclusion obtained was that motivation had positive and significant effect on employee performance. The fourth was by Murdiyanto in 2012 with the research variables were motivation and working environment, and the conclusion obtained was that motivation and working environment had positive and significant effect on employee performance. The fifth was by Thao, J. Hwang in 2015 with the research variables were leadership, organization culture, working environment, motivation, and training, and the conclusion obtained was that leadership, motivation, and training had positive and significant effect on employee performance. The sixth was by Dhermawan, Sudibya, Utama (2012) with the research variables were motivation, working environment, competence, and compensation, and the conclusion obtained was that motivation did not have significant effect on employee performance. The seventh was by Pakpahan, Siswidiyanto, Sukanto (2012) with the research variables were education and training, and the conclusion obtained was that training did not have significant effect on employee performance. The eighth was by Nababan, Tawas, Uhing (2016) with the research variables were education and training, and the conclusion obtained was that education did not have significant effect on employee performance. The ninth was by Utari (2015) with the research variables were motivation, leadership, and discipline, and the conclusion obtained was that discipline did not have significant effect on employee performance. The tenth was by Kelatow, Adolfina, Trang (2016) with the research variables were working evaluation, salary, and working facilities, and the conclusion obtained was that facilities did not have significant effect on employee performance. The eleventh was by Sidanti (2015) with the research variables were working environment, working discipline, and motivation, and the conclusion obtained was that working environment did not have significant effect on employee performance.

The difference between current study and previous studies was the different independent variables as in Hardjono's research in 2013 with working ability; Dhermawan, Sudibya, Utama's research in 2012 with competence and compensation; Utari's research in 2015 with leadership, and Kelatow, Adolfina, Trang's research in 2016 with working evaluation and salary that were not used in this research.

The similarity between current study and previous studies were that the dependent variable used was employee performance and had the same goal which was to find out the factors affecting employee performance. Observing the above discussion, it was required to examine the influence of these variables on employee performance and to understand the problem to be discussed then the problem formulation was how the influence of these variables on employee performance. The aim of this study was to analyze the influence of education, training, motivation, facilities, discipline, and working environment on employee performance.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

Research Object

Graha Puger Sehat Clinic is a first private clinic in Puger District. Graha Puger Sehat Clinic was officially founded at the date of 11 August 2014 with the permission from Health Agency with no. 440/15625/414/2014. The services from Graha Puger Sehat Clinic are General Polyclinic, Dental Polyclinic, Health of Mother and Child-Birth Control Polyclinic (KIA-KB), Inpatient Care, 24 hours Emergency Unit, Pharmacy Unit, and Laboratorium. To provide the best health service for the society of Puger, Graha Puger Sehat Clinic cooperates with Health Social Insurance Administration Organization (BPJS Kesehatan), Employment Social Insurance Administration Organization (BPJS Ketenagakerjaan), and with PT. Cement Puger Jaya Raya Sentosa.

Population and Sample

The population of this study was all employees of Graha Puger Sehat Clinic. According to employee data on the administration unit of Graha Puger Sehat Clinic, there are 42 permanent employees of Graha Puger Sehat Clinic. In this study, the researcher used census method where all employees would be the samples. Based on problem formulation and literature review, the researcher has identified the variables to be used, i.e. employee performance, education, training, facilities, discipline, and working environment.

Research and Measurement Variables

Employee performance as dependent variable can be defined as the result or the success rate of a person as a whole for certain period in carrying out the task in accordance with his responsibility. Education as the first independent variable can be defined as the process of changing the attitudes and behavior of a person or group of people in an effort to mature humans through teaching efforts. This variable is measured through indicators such as mastery of knowledge, attitude in facing the problems, and mastery of a particular field of knowledge. Training as second independent variable is defined as learning process that involves the obtaining of expertise, concept, rules, or behavior to improve employee performance. This variable can be measured through indicators such as the suitability of the materials given in the training, the effectiveness of employees during the work, and how they renew the development of certain sciences. Motivation as the third independent variable can be defined as a factor that encourages a person to perform certain activities. This variable can be measured through indicators such as job security, compensation, and bonuses. Facility as the fourth independent variable can be defined as anything in the form of objects that can facilitate and accelerate work. This variable can be measured through indicators such as health facilities, safety in work, and adequate Clinic facilities. Discipline as the fifth independent variable can be defined as the awareness and willingness of a person to comply with all corporate rules and prevailing social norms. This variable can be measured through indicators such as discipline to come to work punctually, punctual in completing tasks assigned by the chairman, and discipline in complying with existing regulations. The working environment as the sixth independent variable can be defined as everything that exists around the employees and which can influence them in carrying out the tasks they have. This variable can be measured through indicators such as working atmosphere and environmental conditions.

Data collection method used in this study was questionnaire method, interview method and literature method. Data analysis method used in this study was 1) Multiple linear regression analysis, 2) F Test, 3) T-Test, and 4) Analysis of determination coefficient.

3. RESEARCH RESULT ANALYSIS

Data analysis used in this research was divided into 2 parts, the first was according to the description of the statistics with the questionnaire respondents amounted to 42 people with the total return of the questionnaire was 100%. The second was according to the respondents' descriptions: a) The most sex of the respondents was female of 64.3%, while the least respondent is male of 35.7%; b) Most respondents were 20 - 29 years, which was 54.8%, whereas the least respondents were 40 - 49 years, which equaled to 9.5%; and c) Most recent education of the respondents was degree, which was 33.3%, while respondents with junior high school as their last formal education, were the least, which was 2.4%.

By using multiple linear regression analysis, it was found out that the constant was negative (a) which was -1.509. It meant that the employee performance would decrease if several variables as education, training, motivation, facilities, discipline, and working environment not fulfilled. The regression coefficient of education was 0.402, which meant that the higher the level of education the higher the employee performance. The regression coefficient of training was 0.362, which meant that the more training given the higher the employee performance. The regression coefficient of motivation was negative, -0.061, which meant that the more motivation given the less the employee performance. The regression coefficient of facility was 0.656, which meant that the more facilities provided the higher the employee performance. The regression coefficient of discipline was 0.094, which meant that the higher the discipline level of employees the higher the employee performance. The regression coefficient of working environment was 0.883, which meant that the higher the atmosphere of working environment the higher the employee performance.

By using analysis of determination coefficient, the value obtained was 0.544, which meant that simultaneously, there was a significant correlation in the amount of 54.4% between independent factors consisting of education, training, motivation, facilities, discipline, and working environment and employee performance, while the remaining 45.6% was caused by other factors outside the analysis.

By using F test, it was found that the value of F - table (df 6 and 35) was 2.37, while the F - count was 9.150, so the $F\text{-count} > F\text{-table}$ or $9.150 > 2.37$ which meant that simultaneously, there was a significant influence of factors consisting of education, training, motivation, facilities, discipline, and working environment on employee performance.

By using t test, it was found that a) the result obtained for education was $1.141 < 2.03011$, which meant that partially education did not have significant effect on employee performance; b) the result obtained for training was $1.344 < 2.03011$, which meant that partially training did not have significant effect on employee performance; c) the result obtained for motivation was $-0.262 < 2.03011$, which meant that partially motivation did not have significant effect on employee performance; d) the result obtained for facility was $2.459 > 2.03011$, which meant that partially facility had significant effect on employee performance; e) the result obtained for discipline was $0.401 < 2.03011$,

which meant that partially discipline did not have significant effect on employee performance; f) the result obtained for working environment was $2.791 > 2.03011$, which meant that partially working environment had significant effect on employee performance.

4. INTERPRETATION

This study supported previous study conducted by Murdiyanto (2012) that the working environment (X_6) influenced employee performance. Working environment is the most influential in the working atmosphere, especially safe and harmless working environment and good relationships between fellow employees and chairman. The working environment is not only in the form of safe and harmless working environment, but other form of working environments also affect employee spirit in working such as air cleanliness in Clinic working environment, green environment for air exchange, and good lighting.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on data analysis, it was found that education, training, motivation, facility, discipline, and working environment simultaneously had significant effect on employee performance. While partially, the result obtained was that the variables of education, training, motivation, and discipline did not have significant effect on employee performance, and facility significantly influenced employee performance. Working environment was the most dominant variable affecting employee performance.

6. IMPLICATIONS

The improvement of working environment both physical working environment and non-physical working environment affecting the working spirit of employee is required since it will be able to improve employee performance. While other variables such as education, training, motivation, facilities, and discipline still need to be improved.

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